

A Patient-Specific Teleoperation Framework for Lung Ultrasound

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Abstract—In the context of telehealth, AI and robotics enhance personalised care and enable remote examinations such as lung ultrasounds, which gained attention during the COVID-19 pandemic. Due to anatomical variability, teleoperated systems are more practical than autonomous ones. This study presents an anatomy-aware control framework for remote lung ultrasound using biomechanically accurate 3D models for real-time assistance, resulting in significantly reduced examination times compared against the traditional teleoperation methods.

I. INTRODUCTION

Integrating data-driven approaches into telehealth devices improves their predictive capabilities, enabling more accurate diagnoses and personalised treatment plans based on real-time patient data. Advances in robotics, haptics, and virtual reality are enhancing remote visits and surgeries, allowing physicians to examine or operate on patients in different locations using robotic instruments controlled through telehealth interfaces. The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the essential role of telehealth in maintaining healthcare access and preventing disease spread, while also revealing new research challenges. Specifically, in lung ultrasound, researchers are working on developing standardised procedures and enhancing both teleoperated and autonomous robotic systems. Due to significant anatomical variability, fully autonomous systems remain challenging and are not yet ready for widespread clinical use. However, teleoperated systems have shown effectiveness, especially when human decision-making surpasses the capabilities of current autonomous technology. Despite this, these systems still require highly skilled operators to manage complex procedures remotely, which limits their accessibility. To address these challenges, we propose a shared control framework (Figure 1) for lung ultrasound examinations. This system leverages advanced 3D biomechanical models like SMPL [1] and SKEL [2] to provide visual feedback and define forbidden regions for the robot, assisting the physician in precise placements of the probe. Thanks to the reconstructed volumetric and skeletal models of the patient, we are able to enforce constraints to easily position the probe in the intercostal areas and avoid the ribs, improving the safety and efficiency of remote examinations. The results highlight a substantial reduction in the examination time.

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Fig. 1. High level overview of the proposed framework.

II. FRAMEWORK

A. Perception pipeline for patient body modelling

To model the patient’s body, we exploit the Skinned Multi-Person Linear (SMPL) model [1], a linear 3D volumetric body model, described by body pose and shape parameters. Using a skeleton tracker, we initialised the SMPL model with joint positions of the patient. The model parameters were obtained by minimising the chamfer distance and the landmark loss through gradient descent, with respect to the filtered point cloud from an RGB-D camera, segmented using YOLOv8-seg. In this way, we are able to align the SMPL with the point cloud. The skeletal model was obtained with SKEL [2], which approximates the anatomical skeleton within the SMPL model. We aligned SKEL with SMPL by minimising the vertex errors between SMPL and SKEL’s skin. Now we needed a way to classify the areas of the patient’s body surface (i.e. the skin) between target and forbidden regions. The first is a set of points where the practitioner would like to place the probe to acquire ultrasound images; the latter instead represent points to avoid, because the placement of the probe would lead to ultrasound images with shadowing or other undesired artefacts, for example in correspondence of the ribs. To this aim, we annotated six ribs per side relevant for lung ultrasounds and indexed vertices along rib borders. To highlight rib locations under the skin, we projected rib border vertices onto the skin mesh, created a cylindrical projection, and generated a 3D mesh of a curved tube with elliptical cross-section around the central line between the ribs. These tubes define the forbidden region for the teleoperation.

B. Shared Control Strategy

Once the forbidden regions are defined, they are enforced as virtual fixtures (VF) using a constraint optimisation problem, preventing the ultrasound probe mounted on the teleoperated robot from entering these zones during operation. This increases system robustness against operator errors, allowing the probe to move along the VF surface until reaching the desired intercostal area, and avoiding excessive force on the

ribs that could harm the patient. The skeletal model, based on the patient’s unique anatomy, ensures that the forbidden regions, described by meshes, are tailored to the individual. The robot target position, which is sent from the haptic device, is filtered by means of a quadratic optimisation problem with linear constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} & \arg \min_{\Delta \mathbf{x}} \|\Delta \mathbf{x} - \Delta \mathbf{x}_d\|_2, \\ & \text{subject to } \mathbf{A}\Delta \mathbf{x} \geq \mathbf{b} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta \mathbf{x}$ and $\Delta \mathbf{x}_d$ represent the actual and desired position changes of the tool, respectively. Matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{b} define the constraints. The forbidden zones are represented by multiple hyper-planes, each with a normal vector \mathbf{n} and a point \mathbf{p} . The linear constraints ensure that the tool remains on the permissible side of these hyper-planes. A modification accounts for the probe shape by approximating its contact surface as a sphere, adjusting \mathbf{b} to keep the probe outside the forbidden regions. As explained by *Li et al.* [3], we considered only relevant mesh triangles within a defined sphere that bounds all possible positions of the robot end effector in a control cycle. Each triangle within this sphere is analysed to determine the point of minimum distance to the end effector, the closest point (\mathcal{CP}). If \mathcal{CP} lies inside the triangle, no changes are needed. If outside, it is projected onto the nearest edge. The resulting planes are incorporated into the optimisation problem (1) as active constraints, under the conditions reported by the authors in [4].

C. Variable Impedance Control

In human-robot interaction and teleoperation, Cartesian impedance control is commonly utilized because it allows for the regulation of the force exerted by the robot on the environment while maintaining accurate tracking of Cartesian trajectories. This control strategy enables the robot’s end effector to mimic the behaviour of a mass-spring-damper system. While standard approaches presents fixed controller gains (stiffness, damping and inertia), in this framework we exploit an approach where time-varying gains are tuned according to the contact of the probe with stiffer (such as bones) or softer (such as internal organs) materials. In this way, it is possible to further prevent high forces exertion in case of potential mismatches of the anatomical and skeletal models with respect to the real patient. The approach is explained in detail in [5].

III. VALIDATION AND CONCLUSION

The proposed telehealth system is divided into two main components: leader and follower. On the patient side (follower), a 6-dof collaborative robot equipped with force/torque sensors and an ultrasound probe performs the physical examination. The robot is driven by an impedance controller and is remotely teleoperated by a physician using a haptic interface (leader), which transmits the desired pose to the follower and provides force feedback to render the physical interaction with the patient’s body. Two RGB-D cameras, one mounted on the robot’s end-effector and

another fixed on a tripod, monitor the robot’s actions and transmit data to the physician’s graphical user interfaces which replicates the patient’s environment in real-time. Due to the difficulty in objectively assessing the impact of Virtual Fixtures (VF) on ultrasound image acquisition and the lack of standardized image-based metrics to evaluate image quality, we assessed the proposed methodology based on examination duration. We conducted a 4-point frontal ultrasound examination following the protocol by Soldati et al. [6] at the defined frontal areas 11, 12, 13, and 14. A valid acquisition required the pleural line to be visible for at least 90% of its horizontal extent. To reduce bias, the operator trained with the system for 10 minutes prior to the experiment. Tests were alternated with and without VF, totalling 10 trials (5 per condition). Results showed a 26% reduction in examination time with VF. Furthermore, the operator noted reduced cognitive load and increased confidence during free motion, linked to easier target point identification. A limitation of using only RGB images was the occlusion of the camera view by the end effector, complicating interactions. However, this issue was mitigated with 3D visual feedback (VF), which consistently displayed the probe’s position in the ribs region.

In conclusion, this study tackles the challenge of patient-specificity in robotic lung ultrasound. By using a model that captures both the pose and shape of the human body, we generated an anatomical skeleton. From this, we developed an automated method to create VF that constrain the robot’s movements to intercostal regions. The framework was validated measuring the execution times for four frontal areas in a clinically validated protocol. The results demonstrated a significant reduction in the protocol execution time, highlighting a promising avenue for research. Future work will focus on integrating real-time measurements, such as contact force, to enhance the body model with viscoelastic properties, as shown in [5], and to mitigate the limitations of vision-based methods. Further studies involving more clinicians and a larger pool of subjects are also planned.

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